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THE MAIN ASPECTS OF INFORMATIONAL PROVIDING
FOR THE UN PEACEKEEPING

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The main goal of the article is to analyze the main problems of information support for the UN peacekeeping. Over the past decades, leading political leaders and experts have always paid very serious attention to information problems. Among foreign researchers, substantiating the role of information in the world, it is necessary to single out the works of A. Gore, Z. Brzezinski, M. Makluhan, A. Toffler and others. The UN Secretaries-General continue to pay great attention to information development, among which they made a special contribution to the information support of peacekeeping B. Gali and K. Annan. Among Ukrainian scientists exploring the role of information, information relations and the role of international organizations in them, I would like to highlight Pocheptsov G. G., Zernetskaya O. V., Litvinenko A. V. and Makarenko E. A. Among the works of Ukrainian researchers regarding the UN peacekeeping work, it is worth noting the work of V. S. Brus, L. I. Skorokhod and Y. S. Skorokhod and others.

In the study of the UN information system, systemic and analytical methods were used. The historical approach allowed us to trace the evolution of UN activities in the field of information support for peacekeeping. The article analyzes the problems of information support for UN peacekeeping. The main elements of the concept of peacekeeping operations are highlighted. The foundations of the theory and practice of UN activities in the field of peacekeeping and its information support are considered. The main UN units involved in peacekeeping operations and their cooperation in the information sphere are analyzed.

Conclusions have been made regarding the future of UN peacekeeping, which will depend on the Organization's ability to ensure the unity of objectives of its various departments, funds and programs, allow it to act in concert and use its resources in strategically important areas.

Key words: UN information activities; informational providing; UN peacekeeping operations; Department of Peace Operations.

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Головні аспекти інформаційного забезпечення миротворчої діяльності ООН

Головною метою статті є аналіз основних проблем інформаційного забезпечення миротворчої діяльності ООН. Протягом останніх десятиліть провідні політичні лідери та експерти завжди приділяли інформаційним проблемам серйозну увагу. Серед закордонних дослідників, що обґрунтовували роль інформації у світі, необхідно виділити роботи А. Гора, З. Бжезинського, М. Маклухана, А. Тоффлера та ін. Велику увагу інформаційному розвитку продовжують приділяти Генеральні секретарі ООН, серед яких особливий внесок в інформаційне забезпечення миротворчості зробили Б. Галі та К. Аннан. Серед українських учених, що досліджують роль інформації, інформаційні відносини та роль міжнародних організацій в них, слід виділити Г. Г. Почепцова, О. В. Зернецьку, О. В. Литвиненка та Є. А. Макаренко. Серед праць українських дослідників, які стосуються миротворчої роботи ООН, варто відзначити В. С. Бруза, Л. І. Скороход, Ю. С. Скорохода та ін.

У дослідженні інформаційної системи ООН застосовувалися системний і аналітичний методи. Історичний підхід дозволив простежити еволюцію діяльності ООН в області інформаційного забезпечення миротворчості. У статті аналізуються проблеми інформаційного забезпечення миротворчої діяльності ООН. Висвітлено основні елементи концепції операцій з підтримки миру. Розглянуто основи теорії і практики діяльності ООН в галузі підтримання миру та її інформаційного забезпечення. Проаналізовано основні підрозділи ООН, що займаються миротворчими операціями та їх співробітництво в інформаційній сфері.

Зроблено висновки щодо майбутнього миротворчої діяльності ООН, яка буде залежати від здатності Організації забезпечувати єдність цілей її різних департаментів, фондів і програм, що дозволить їй діяти узгоджено і використовувати свої ресурси на стратегічно важливих напрямках.

Ключові слова: інформаційна діяльність ООН; інформаційне забезпечення; миротворчі операції ООН; Департамент операцій з підтримання миру.

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Главные аспекты информационного обеспечения миротворческой деятельности ООН

Главной целью статьи является анализ основных проблем информационного обеспечения миротворческой деятельности ООН.

На протяжении последних десятилетий ведущие политические лидеры и эксперты всегда уделяли информационным проблемам серьезное внимание. Среди зарубежных исследователей, обосновывали роль информации в мире, необходимо выделить работы А. Гора, З. Бжезинского, М. Маклухана, А. Тоффлера и др. Большое внимание информационному развитию продолжают уделять Генеральные секретари ООН, среди которых особый вклад в информационное обеспечение миротворчества сделали Б. Гали и К. Аннан. Среди украинских ученых, исследующих роль информации, информационные отношения и роль международных организаций в них, хотелось бы выделить Г. Г. Почепцова, О. В. Зернецкую, А. В. Литвиненко и Е. А. Макаренко. Среди работ украинских исследователей, касающиеся миротворческой работы ООН, стоит отметить работы В. С. Бруза, Л. И. Скороход, Ю. С. Скорохода и др.

При исследовании информационной системы ООН применялись системный и аналитический методы. Исторический подход позволил проследить эволюцию деятельности ООН в области информационного обеспечения миротворчества. В статье анализируются проблемы информационного обеспечения миротворческой деятельности ООН. Освещены основные элементы концепции операций по поддержанию мира. Рассмотрены основы теории и практики деятельности ООН в области поддержания мира и ее информационного обеспечения. Проанализированы основные подразделения ООН, занимающиеся миротворческими операциями и их сотрудничество в информационной сфере.

Сделаны выводы относительно будущего миротворческой деятельности ООН, которое будет зависеть от способности Организации обеспечивать единство целей ее различных департаментов, фондов и программ, позволит ей действовать согласованно и использовать свои ресурсы на стратегически важных направлениях.

Ключевые слова: информационная деятельность ООН; информационное обеспечение; миротворческие операции ООН; Департамент операций по поддержанию мира.

Introduction

One of the main reasons for the creation of the UN and the main part of its powers is to ensure international peace and security. Since its inception, the UN has repeatedly warned of the threat of disputes escalating into open hostilities, urging the warring parties to use the negotiating table instead of weapons, helping to restore peace where the conflict got out of control. Peacekeeping is part of the much broader effort that the UN is making for peace. The UN uses preventive diplomacy to eliminate the conflict before it explodes, as well as post-conflict peace building to create

conditions for sustainable peace and address the causes of a new conflict. At all these stages, using the information industry is vital.

The main factor that influenced the functioning of the UN is that policy issues have gone beyond sectors and countries. Sustainable development, relief operations, the link between humanitarian assistance and development cooperation cross sectoral and institutional boundaries. It should also be noted that the pace of change is accelerating. As a result of the information revolution, policy makers and the public are more aware of how today's actions can affect the future. Now that the value of the time factor has changed dramatically, the responsiveness and flexibility of any organization is especially appreciated.

Analysis of the previous publications and researches

The basics of the theory and practice of UN activities in the field of peacekeeping and its information support are set forth in such reports of the UN Secretary General as "Agenda for Peace: Preventive Diplomacy, Peacekeeping and Peacekeeping" by B. B. Gali (Gali, 1992) and "We, the Peoples: the role of the UN in the XXI century" K. Annan (Annan, 2000).

Specifying the purpose of research

The main goal of the article is to analyze the main problems of information support for the UN peacekeeping, while addressing such methods of study as system, systemic and analytical methods. The historical approach allowed us to trace the evolution of UN activities in the field of information support for peacekeeping.

Presenting the research material

In the field of peace and security, the UN is mainly concerned with intra-state conflicts, often has serious international consequences and is often associated with humanitarian emergencies. Recent trends indicate that conflicts of this kind will continue to require UN priority attention.

Currently, the concept of peacekeeping operations (peacekeeping operations) has been formed, the elements of which can be formulated as follows: peacekeeping operations are carried out primarily to prevent conflicts and resolve disputes peacefully; the preparation and conduct of such operations is closely coordinated with regional organizations and associated with a political settlement and guarantees from the Security Council or its permanent members; the scope of the application of peacekeeping forces is expanding; deals are combined to solve economic, social and humanitarian problems of the respective countries and regions; a unified system of training national contingents is being created; establishes the legal and financial basis for the activities of peacekeeping forces.

Among the main ways of ensuring peace and security, preventive diplomacy, peacekeeping, peacekeeping and post-conflict peace building are noted. The most desirable and effective use of diplomacy is before tensions escalate into conflict, or if it begins, by taking immediate measures to deter and eliminate its causes.

The UN needs early warning, information gathering and analysis of facts. For this, an exchange of military missions may take place; regional hazard reduction centres could be established; there should be a free flow of information and monitoring the implementation of agreements.

Preventive steps should be based on timely and accurate facts. For the UN, the necessary information should cover economic and social trends, as well as political events. It is necessary to apply the fact-finding procedure more often. Detailed information is also often provided by the Secretary General's contacts with the governments of member states. In addition, the Secretary General sends senior officials for consultations. All states should be prepared to provide the information necessary for the effective functioning of the UN. Fact-finding missions are authorized by the Security Council or the UN General Assembly. In addition, these missions can help resolve disputes by their presence alone.

In the field of early warning, there is a need to strengthen the mechanism so that it is possible to synthesize information with political indicators to determine the threat to peace and UN actions. The results of the analysis should be reported to the Security Council and the UN General Assembly. In addition, B. Gali invited ECOSOC to submit reports on economic and social events that could be a threat to peace. A major role in early warning should be given to regional mechanisms and organizations. The Secretary General emphasized the importance for all organizations of establishing liaison with the UN for taking security measures (Gali, 1992).

Peacekeeping can be considered a UN invention. It helped stabilize the situation in many areas of tension in the world. The principles of this activity quickly adapt to the requirements of the time, although the basis remains unchanged: a clear and real mandate; cooperation of the parties in its execution; support from the Security Council; the willingness of Member States to provide their military, police and civilian personnel with effective UN management; appropriate financial and logistical support.

Without post-conflict peace building, all previous achievements will not have such a meaning for the lives of people in the conflict zone. For real success, Peacekeeping operations (PKO) must include efforts to establish and maintain the structures necessary to strengthen peace and enhance confidence and well-being. Such activities may include, but are not limited to: advising staff to ensure security, monitoring elections, protecting human rights, reforming and strengthening government institutions. After an international war, such measures include the implementation of specific projects linking countries, the promotion of socio-economic development, confidence-building, joint agricultural development, cultural and educational exchanges.

UN Secretary General K. Annan in his report "We, the peoples: the role of the UN in the XXI century" outlined the main directions and principles

of the Organization's activities in the field of ensuring peace and security in our time (Annan, 2000). According to the UN Secretary General, it is more than a simple tool – it is designed to introduce new principles into international relations. How far the world has gone from a purely international one is evidenced by the nature of the current threats to peace and security. The provisions of the Charter are based on the assumption that external aggression is the most serious threat, but in recent decades, many more people have been killed as a result of civil wars, ethnic cleansing and acts of genocide. The UN has not yet adapted its institutions to this new reality.

Formal organizational structures often lack the breadth of coverage, speed and information potential, which allow them to keep up with the rapid changes in the world. Therefore, the mobilization of resources of various global forces may be associated with the formation of non-rigid global networks for policy issues that do not recognize borders. Such networks can be virtual in nature, allowing you to overcome the usual obstacles of distance and time. It is the UN that is well suited to support such coalitions.

Thanks to the end of the Cold War, the UN began to play a more prominent role. Its activities both in support and in establishing peace were sharply intensified. Since 2000s, wars were fought mainly within states. These wars did not so much erase borders as they killed people. At the beginning of the XXIst century, after all these conflicts, a new concept of security is being formed. Whereas previously ensuring security meant protecting the territory from external attack, now it includes protecting the entire population and specific people from violence generated within the state.

These new challenges are forcing the UN to adjust traditional concepts, but one thing remains true: you need to start with prevention. Poor countries have less economic and political resources to resolve conflicts. This means that reducing poverty and achieving economic growth is a step towards conflict prevention. Therefore, all those involved in conflict prevention must solve all these problems in a complex. But even the best containment strategies can lead to failure, and so other measures may be needed. One of them is the willingness to protect vulnerable people. In this regard, the wider use of information technology can help reduce the suffering for people during emergencies.

While the focus of traditional peacekeeping operations was mainly on ceasefire monitoring efforts, today's comprehensive peacekeeping operations are of a completely different nature. Their goal is to help conflicting parties secure their interests by political means. To this end, the UN contributes to the creation and strengthening of political institutions, as well as expanding their base. The organization works with governments and local communities to deliver humanitarian assistance, reintegrate ex-combatants into society, mine, build

communications, prepare and conduct elections, and promote sustainable development.

Like all activities of the UN General Assembly Secretariat, PKOs are carried out under the general direction of the Secretary General. Almost all Secretariat units are involved to one degree or another in providing advice and assistance to the Secretary General in planning or coordinating the management of these operations.

In the Office of the Secretary-General, five units are associated with peace support. The Secretary General's Administrative Office assists him in maintaining contact with senior peacekeeping officials. In addition, employees inform the Deputy Secretary General for Special Political Cases of all activities related to an existing or future peacekeeping operation and advise him on various aspects of such activities. The Office for Special Political Affairs provides advice and assistance to the Secretary General in the performance of his functions related to the implementation of the PKO and their management. The Assistant Secretary General draws up plans for new peacekeeping operations and manages existing operations. It produces tactical installations and operational instructions for UN operations commanders. The military adviser advises the Secretary General and his deputy on military aspects of operations at all stages from their planning to practical implementation.

In the Office of Research and Information Collection, the Assistant Secretary General, who heads the Office and his staff, is responsible for the research, collection and dissemination of information within the Secretariat regarding the functions of the Secretary General. In this capacity, they work closely with the Deputy Secretary General for Special Political Affairs and give him the relevant information at their disposal, which may have consequences for the initiation or implementation of the PKO.

The Department of Administration and Management plays an important role in the planning and organization of new PKOs. The Department includes the General Services Office, manages three organizational units, which include the Field Operations Department, the Commercial Operations, Procurement and Transportation Service, and the Telecommunications and Machine Operations Service. The field operations department has a specific information function. Its services include, in particular, logistics, inventory management, communications, coordination with governments, travel arrangements (military and civilian personnel), financial matters, and electronic data processing. The responsibilities of the Commercial Operations, Procurement and Transportation Service include the procurement of materials and equipment for UN field missions. The Telecommunication and Machine Operations Service carries out telecommunications support for PKOs at Headquarters, including messaging, maintenance of communication lines, etc.

Other departments, in particular, the Department of Political Affairs and the Department of Conference Services, are also involved in peacekeeping operations. The main Department on Peace and Security is usually the DPO (Department of Peace Operations), formerly known as DPKO (Department of Peacekeeping Operations). It has a very large number of functions related to information activities. It serves as the operational unit of the Secretary General for all peacekeeping operations and is responsible for the management, management, planning and preparation of these operations; prepares reports of the Secretary-General to the Security Council and the General Assembly on selected PKOs, on peacekeeping in general, and mine clearance; coordinates all UN mine action activities; provides secretariat services to the Special Committee with PKO; based on decisions of the Security Council, develops policies and procedures for the establishment of new PKOs; develops operational plans and methodology for multifaceted operations; carries out advance planning for possible new PKOs and related activities; liaises with parties to the conflict and members of the Security Council regarding the effective implementation of Security Council decisions; liaises with Member States, UN agencies and other organizations and coordinates their participation in operations; prepares guidelines and principles on training for member states contributing contingents to PKO (Department of Peace Operations).

Conclusions

Considering the issues of cooperation in the UN system on ensuring peace and security, it should be noted that an important achievement was the establishment of close working relations of the Department of global communications (DGC), formerly known as DPI (Department of Public Information) with the DPO, as well as the Department of Political Affairs and the Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. Given the opinion of the Secretary General that information and communication should be at the very centre of the UN strategic management, we can say that all the structures that concern this have recognized that public information and communication will become the main part of their activities. As a result of efforts to improve cooperation and coordination between the relevant departments, DGC is involved in consultations and preparatory work in the initial stages of the deployment of peacekeeping missions and other field missions. This allows the relevant departments to allocate adequate resources for the information components of such missions on a planned basis, and not from case to case. DGC now acts as a focal point for supporting activities in the field of public information and communication during field operations. The DGC conducted a thorough study and review of the experience of the PKO, which allowed the development of relevant guidelines for the creation and functioning of public information and communication components during field operations.

Ensuring close coordination with the Peace and Security Section of the DGC is one of the key elements of a strategy that cannot be effectively implemented without cooperation between the two departments. The DGC, in turn, invited DPO to participate in discussions on strategic communications.

So, in the future, success will depend on the ability of the UN to ensure the unity of goals of its various departments, funds and programs, which will allow it to act in concert and use its resources in strategically important areas. In order to succeed in the future, the UN must focus on the aspects of activity, resorting to it better than others do. It is also necessary that the UN develop effective methods of cooperation with other international organizations, strengthening the influence of its moral values.

The author is confident that peace in a broad sense cannot be achieved only through the efforts of the UN and member governments. Everyone needs to be involved in such activities: NGOs, the media and the general public. This will strengthen the ability of the UN to reflect the problems of those it represents, and will provide a better opportunity to disseminate information about the UN and foster understanding of its activities.

References:

1. Annan, K. A. (2000). *We the peoples: the role of the United Nations in the XXIst century*. New York: UN.
2. Department of Peace Operations. *United Nations*, [website]. Available at: [http:// https://peacekeeping.un.org/ru/departement-of-peace-operations](http://https://peacekeeping.un.org/ru/departement-of-peace-operations).
3. Gali, B. B. (1992). *An agenda for the world. Preventive diplomacy, peacemaking and peacekeeping*. New York: DPI.

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